

autoFISH: how to use the software to control the automated fluidics system

Short name: autofish_software-manual
Version: 2
Date: 1.3.2025

This document describes the use of the Python-based autoFISH software to control an automated fluidics system. It allows alternating between buffer-exchange cycles and imaging.

- Before starting, **we recommend skimming over the entire documentation** to get a feel for how this package works. Some things might otherwise be confusing.
- **TESTED FOR WIN 10 only:** most microscope control packages work only under Windows.

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1 Overview

Here, we briefly overview how autoFISH works and the components required. The subsequent chapters provide a more detailed description.

In short, autoFISH is a Python package that performs sequential fluidic runs on a microscope, alternating between complex buffer exchanges and automating image acquisition.

- The **used fluidics system** is homemade, based on widely available, low-cost components. It is based on published approaches ((Bintu et al., 2018; Moffitt and Zhuang, 2016).
- **Image acquisition** is performed using the Python package PycroManager (Pinkard et al., 2021) or via simple synchronization with a shared text file.

Python controls the entire workflow and allows additional data-processing steps if required, e.g., image analysis to verify data integrity or to pre-process data to save time.

1.1 Configurations: demo and standard experiments

We provide **demo configuration** files that allow testing of the different modules without connecting to actual hardware. This allows testing a proper installation of autoFISH. Demo configurations are available in the [demo subfolder](#). We also refer to these demo tests in the respective sections.

1.2 Fluidics system

We use a custom-build fluidics system to perform the liquid handling. It allows to automatically perform buffer exchanges.

We provide detailed building plans in the dedicated document found [here](#).

1.3 Microscope control

1. We provide several options to start acquisitions on a microscope.
2. Image acquisition can be performed with the Python package **PycroManager** (Pinkard et al., 2021). This allows the launching of multi-D acquisition events with Micromanager 2.
3. Synchronization can also be done with a **shared text file**. Two options exist:
 - a. **Content** of the text file: set to 1 to start the acquisition. The acquisition software must return 0 once the imaging is terminated. Then, the next fluidic run is started.
 - b. **Presence** of text file: autoFISH creates this text file to indicate that the acquisition should be started. Once the acquisition is terminated, the acquisition software must delete the file to signal that imaging is terminated.
4. **TTL synchronization**. This option allows communication with acquisition software via TTL pulses, e.g., with LEICA microscopes. The current implementation relies on a microcontroller (Arduino or Raspberry Pi) to send and receive TTL pulses. These controllers are cheap and easy to set up.

1.4 New contributions

We develop autoFISH in a modular and extensible fashion. This design makes it easy to add new hardware components, such as a different pump, or define a new acquisition routine.

If you want to integrate your own development in autoFISH, you can create a pull request on GitHub, and after verification, we can integrate these. Alternatively, you can also contact us to discuss how best to integrate your contribution.

2 Software installation

The code is hosted on GitHub: <https://github.com/fish-quant/autofish>.

Below is one workflow for getting started; many others exist.

2.1 Install miniconda and autoFISH

You only must do this for installation or updates.

1. Download the latest **version of miniconda** (Python 3.X) from <https://docs.conda.io/en/latest/mini-conda.html>.
2. Open an Anaconda terminal and create a dedicated environment:
`conda create --name autofish python=3.10`
3. Activate the environment:
`conda activate autofish`
4. Install autoFISH:
`pip install autofish`

2.1.1 Development installation

You can also download autoFISH from GitHub

1. Create the conda environment as above (steps 1-3)
2. Open the Anaconda terminal and navigate to the location where you want to install autofish
`conda activate autofish`
`git clone https://github.com/fish-quant/autofish.git`
`cd autofish`
`pip install . -e`

2.2 Starting autoFISH

1. Activate the environment:
`conda activate autofish`
2. Start the user interface
`autofish`

2.3 Upgrade autoFISH to the latest version

3. Activate environment:
`conda activate autofish`
4. Start the user interface
`pip install -upgrade autofish`

2.4 For developers

We use Visual Studio Code for development, but of course, any Python IDE works. The installation link is [here](#).

2.4.1 Change the default terminal to Command Prompt

Under Windows, we had some issues when using PowerShell as a Terminal; switching to Command Prompt resolved them. To do this, perform the following steps in Visual Studio Code.

1. Open Visual Studio Code.
2. Press CTRL + SHIFT + P to open the Command Palette.
3. Search for `Terminal: Select Default Profile`

4. Select `Command Prompt`

2.4.2 Setting up Visual Studio Code

1. Launch Visual Studio Code.
2. From the menu `File > Add folder to workspace`
3. Select the folder containing the Python code.
4. Double-click on the file `coordinator_gui.py` located in the autofish folder.
5. Running this script opens the autoFISH user interface by pressing the Run symbol (arrow) above the code editor window.
6. The first time, you must specify:
 - a. ... the conda environment you defined above.
 - b. ... if you would like to install the Python extension, accept.
7. You can save this workspace to a file, which can then be opened for subsequent usage, and which will also remember the conda environment: `File > Save workspace as`

3 A typical autoFISH experiment

We provide various simple user interfaces for defining microscopy and fluidics. These are explained in dedicated sections below. The entry point is a **launch pad** (opened with the command `autofish`), which permits access to these control interfaces and starts the complete run.

3.1 A typical autoFISH experiment

Below, we describe a typical workflow for an autoFISH experiment. The following sections explain each step in more detail.

1. Open the **fluidics interface** to define the fluidics run. This includes specifying the sequence of buffer exchanges and priming the tubing to prepare the system. Please note that you can also run selected cycles without an acquisition.
2. Specify acquisition in the **acquisition software**, e.g., Micromanager.
3. Setup acquisition in autoFISH.
4. Initiate the controller to permit a fully automated run.
5. Run the entire fluidics run.

3.1.1 Considerations

- Only the first round contains a **DAPI** stain. Only for this round is the DAPI image acquired.
- **Imaging settings** are defined after the first round, since cells are visible here.
- For the remaining rounds, the experiment is automated.

3.1.2 Preparation

1. Get **samples** ready:
 - Mount the imaging chamber.
 - Prepare all buffers.
2. Prepare **autoFISH** system:
 - a. Define experimental settings in the config file.
 - b. Start the fluidics flow sensor and start logging to a file.
 - c. Start autoFISH and initiate (config files, zero robot)
 - d. Prime lines and check flow (replace tubing if necessary)
 - e. Hardware (easy to forget)
 - f. Temperature control (both objective and chamber)
 - g. Vacuum pump

3.1.3 Actual experiment (PycroManager as an example)

1. Run the first hybridization round (including DAPI)
2. PycroManager: define acquisition.
 - Include the DAPI channel.
 - Save the position list.
3. autoFISH: setup imaging
 - a. Adjust the microscope configuration file for channels and z-stacks.
 - b. Open the PycroManager module in autoFISH
 - i. Load config files (position, microscope)
 - ii. Specify a folder to save images.
 - iii. Perform acquisition for the first round.
4. Start automated runs.
 - a. Initiate the controller.
 - b. Launch all runs.

3.1.4 Turning of system

1. Clean system: flush all fluidic lines with water.
2. Turn off all hardware.
3. Detach the tubing from the peristaltic pump.

3.2 Other scenarios

3.2.1 Acquisition specification after the first run

Often, the **acquisition is defined after the first fluidics run**, i.e., because no labeling was performed on the bench. Here, you can run the first run manually in the fluidics interface, define your acquisition, and acquire images for this first run before switching to automated mode.

3.2.2 Acquisition of additional channels

If you acquire **additional channels** in the first round, e.g., DAPI, we recommend **acquiring them last**. **This way**, the numeric channel identifiers will not be mixed up; e.g., FISH will always be the first channel acquired.

4 Microscopy control

In the pulldown menu of the launchpad, you can select the microscope synchronization you would like to use.

4.1 Text file synchronization

A shared text file establishes communication between autoFISH and the image acquisition software. Implementations exist in two flavors:

- This text file **contains** 1 to indicate that the acquisition should be launched, and it must be set back to 0 by the acquisition software once the imaging is terminated.
- A text file is **created** to indicate that the acquisition has been launched and must be deleted to signal to the acquisition software once imaging is terminated.

4.1.1 Typical workflow

1. Select "Text file sync" from the dropdown menu in the main interface, then press `Microscope`.
2. In the interface, select the text file you want to see to communicate with the acquisition software.
3. Create the acquisition object by pressing the corresponding button.
4. You can then close the interface.

4.1.2 Demo

If you want to test alternating sequences of fluidics run and imaging, you could load the demo config for the fluidics. When you launch the entire run, you can manually set the sync file back to 0 to indicate that imaging is complete.

4.2 TTL synchronization

Here, image synchronization is obtained with TTL pulses. To achieve this, we use a widely available microcontroller (Arduino). These controllers can send/receive TTL pulses. autoFISH communicates with this controller via the serial port.

In autoFISH,

- **To start an acquisition** after a completed fluidic run, the string `start` is sent to the Arduino
- The system will **wait** until it receives the string `finished`. Then the next fluidics run is initiated.

On the **Arduino**, an event loop is running. It reads the serial port until the string `starts` is received. It will then send an output TTL trigger. It will then wait for an input TTL trigger and, once received, send the string `finished` via the serial port to autoFISH.

Setting up an Arduino is simple (see instructions for construction of the fluidics system for more details). The code running on the Arduino is [here](#).

Communication with the Arduino is established [via settings file](#) shown below. The most important part is the COM part, where the Arduino is connected.

```
{
  "TTL": {
    "type": "arduino",
```

```
"COM": "COM13",  
"baudrate": 9600,  
"parity": "even"  
}  
}
```

4.2.1 Typical workflow

1. In the main autoFISH interface, under `Specify acquisition`, select `TTL sync`
2. In the interface, select the TTL sync file from above
3. Press `Connect to TTL sync` box

4.2.2 Fixed duration to start fluidics

We encountered issues with the 'finished' signal being received prematurely. In this case, you can add a fixed time to the TTL specification file from above. For this, add an additional line

```
"wait_time": 60
```

Here, the system will wait for 600s (10 min) before the next fluidics run is performed. Attention: this duration should be longer than the actual imaging time to avoid activating the fluidics system during imaging.

4.3 PycroManager

Here, the acquisition is performed with Micromanager 2 (Edelstein et al., 2014) using the Python package PycroManager (Pinkard et al., 2021). This requires installing the latest nightly build of the micromanager from [here](#).

4.3.1 Micromanager, PycroManager, headless

We refer to PycroManager's excellent documentation for guidance on getting started and verifying that the installation works properly. PycroManager allows **headless connections** to Micromanager. This means no open instance of the micromanager is required, and only essential elements of the micromanager core are started from within Python. In our hands, this allowed for more stable acquisitions.

4.3.2 Typical workflow

1. We usually open a micromanager instance to **set up the acquisition**:
 - a. Finding adequate **exposure times** for the different channels.
 - b. Specifying the **different positions** that should be acquired. These positions are then exported as a position list for import into autoFISH.
2. Micromanager can be closed at this stage if a headless acquisition is performed.
3. Update the microscope configuration file (see below) to specify the z-range and the channels to be acquired.
4. In the Python autoFISH GUI, select `pycromanager` from the dropdown menu and press `Specify acquisition`. This will open the window shown below:
 - a. Load configuration file.
 - b. Load position list.
 - c. Specify the folder to save images.
 - d. Connect to Micromanager.
 - e. Create the acquisition event.
 - f. [Optional] Launch a test acquisition. This can also be used to acquire the images of the first fluidics run.

- 5.
6. The interface can now be closed (unless you want to perform different acquisitions for the first round as for the remaining ones).

4.3.3 Microscope configuration

All acquisition parameters, except the position lists, are specified in the file `microscope_config.yaml`

Some parameters are specific to your microscope, such as the name of the XY and Z drive; the provided names are for an inverted Nikon Ti. You might need to adapt this for your microscope.

A typical file is shown below:

```
Microscope:
  type: 'NIKON_TI'
  xy_drive_name: 'TIXYDrive'
  Core-TimeoutMs: 1500
  stage-speed: 6
  z_drive_name: 'TIZDrive'
  channel_group: 'channels'
  channels: ['Cy3_75', 'DAPI_5']
  channel_exposures_ms: [100,50]
  channel_blank: DAPI_0
  z_start: 0
  z_end: 6
  z_step: 0.4
  mm_app_path: 'C:\Program Files\Micro-Manager-2.0-nightly'
  mm_config_file: 'MMConfig_demo.cfg'
```

The different fields are described next. Most of these are specific for a NikonTi widefield microscope. Adding support for other microscopes can be achieved by modifying the autoFISH codebase.

Command	Action
type	Specify your microscope. This will essentially determine how the position list is read (see function <code>load_position_list</code> in <code>imager.py</code>) Currently implemented are <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demo: for test purposes only with demo MM config file. Small position list is created. Allows testing the PycroManager installation. • NIKON_TI: for an inverted Nikon Ti.
xy_drive_name z_drive_name	Names of the XY and Z drives. Will depend on your microscope. These are used to interpret the loaded positions lists.
stage_speed	Speed at which the stage is moving. For NikonTi from 1 (fast) to 8 (slow). We use slower speeds when larger displacements are performed, e.g. for Ibididi multi-channel slides. This helps to keep the autofocus system engaged.

Core-TimeoutMs	Time-out for Core after which an error will be shown. Default is 5000, we set this to higher values when the stage moves slowly.
channel_group	Name of channel group containing the channels that will be acquired.
channels	List of all channels that will be acquired.
channel_exposures_ms	List of exposure times (in ms) of the acquired channels specified in channel.
channel_blank	[optional] Channel name used for a blank acquisition. When specified one additional image will be taken at the first position without a z-stack using this channel. This can be necessary when the light source is not automatically turned off after acquisition.
z_start z_end z_step	Positions of z-stack relative to specified Z-position in position list.

The following parameters are only needed for the headless start of micromanager

mm_app_path	Path to micromanager
mm_config_file	Name of micromanager config file

4.3.4 Position list

The different positions that should be acquired are stored in a .pos file. In autoFISH, these positions are then read into Python as XYZ coordinates (`imager.py > pycromanager > load_position_list`). This routine might need to be adapted to your microscope.

4.3.5 Demo

You can load the demo file `microscope_config_demo.yaml`.

You have two different options.

1. Open micromanager and connect normally.
2. Update the micromanager path and name of the config file and connect headless.

4.3.6 Known issues

If you see error messages complaining about ZMQ, a likely explanation is that you don't have the latest nightly build of Micromanager and/or the latest version of PycroManager. Try to download the latest Micromanager version, and update PycroManager:

1. Open conda terminal
2. Activate environment:
`conda activate autofish`
3. Update pycromanager:
`pip install -U pycromanager`

4.4 Adding your own acquisition module

The autoFISH code is modular, and you can add your own acquisition routine. However, this will require some coding. As guidance, you can already look at how the existing two imaging routines are implemented.

- You will need to add a new Class in `imager.py` (using Microscope) as a parent class. As a minimum, this class needs to provide a function called `acquire_images`. This function will launch the desired acquisition routine.
- In `coordinator.py`, you will need to add your new acquisition class to the function `run_all_rounds` to correctly handle the potential input parameters.
- In `coordinator_gui.py`, you will need to add your class to the dropdown menu of the launch GUI (`make_window_control`), and then write the GUI for your calls that collect the relevant user inputs.

5 Setting up the fluidics system

We next describe how to set up the fluidic system and define a sequence of steps to be performed automatically. The fluidics system consists of at least a **pump** and the **pipette robot**; optionally, it can further contain a computer-controlled valve and flow sensor

5.1 Configuration files

For a user, 2 files are important: they define how Python interacts with the different components and how the actual experiment is defined.

- `system_config.json`: specifies how to communicate with the different hardware components (pump, valve, CNC robot). This must be adapted to a given fluidics system only once and then remains unchanged. For more details, see the dedicated section in the [Appendix](#).
- `experiment_config.yaml`: specifies where the buffers are and the sequence of a run. Has to be adapted for each experiment. For more details, see the dedicated section about [experiment specifications](#).

5.2 Basic usage of the fluidic system

The fluidics system can be controlled and initiated via the user interface shown below. We next detail a typical workflow; more details on the config files are provided in subsequent sections.

1. Make sure hardware specifications stored in `system_config.json` are correct.
2. Update the robot configuration file, `robot_config.yaml` for your experiment.
3. Turn on the fluidics system (pump, robot, (if present) valve, (if present) start flow measurement.
4. Start autoFISH; this will show the GUI.
5. Initiate system (Step 1 in GUI, red).
 - a. Press `Browse` to select fluidics specification file.
 - b. Press `Initiate robot & ...` to initiate communication with the different components.
6. Zero CNC robot over well A1 (Step 2 in GUI, blue)
 - a. Move robot with jog buttons for indicated distance in mm. Center over well A1 (a few mm above)
IMPORTANT: don't move too much, robot doesn't know the limits of the different motors.
 - b. Once the needle is centered over A1, press `Zero stage`
7. Load robot specification file (Step 3 in GUI, green). This will verify which buffers are used for the sequential runs, estimate the total run time, and calculate the position of each well. Some information is provided in the terminal, more details in the log file.
8. Prime buffer lines (without the chamber attached) (Step 4, purple)

- a. Select the buffer you want to prime from the pulldown menu. Press `Go to buffer.`
 - b. Press the `Start pump` to turn it on for the indicated duration in seconds. The pump can only be started once. To start again, the buffer must be selected.
9. Connect the sample support (chamber, ...) and prime
 - a. Fill with buffer
 - b. Chase bubbles.
 - c. Mount on the microscope
 10. [Optional] If you want to run a selected round, select it from the drop-down menu and press `RUN sequence` (Step 5, orange)
 11. Progress will be shown in the terminal. A more detailed log is created in a file.
 12. Once the round is terminated, it will be removed from the dropdown list.

5.3 Experiment specification: `experiment_config.yaml`

This file contains information on the buffers, the buffer exchange sequence, and the plate robot layout.

- Stored as a yaml file.
- Strict formatting: spacing and indents must be respected.
- The file contains three sections defining the entire experiment. Each section starts with the respective keyword followed by a ":". Elements of each section have an indent of 4 spaces.
 - **buffers:** name and position of all buffers.
 - **sequence:** sequence of steps the robot must perform for each run.
- **well_plate:** properties of the plate robot.

5.3.1 buffers

Here, the names and positions of all buffers are specified. **Two types of buffers** can be specified:

- **General-purpose buffers:** they are the same for each round. Typically stored in syringes.
- Hybridization round-specific buffers: they change during each round.
 - These are typically buffers with readout oligos or specific wash buffers. Several such buffers can be defined for a round.
 - The buffers are declared in the 'sequence' section and terminate with an **ii**, e.g., `w_ii`. In the buffer list, each item is given a unique name for each round, e.g., `w_r1` for round `r1`.
 - **At least one** hybridization-specific buffer must be specified. Autofish analyses the settings file and then automatically determines the round identifiers.
- Runs are listed and executed in the order the buffer list is provided.

5.3.1.1 Names

- Each name must be **unique**.
- Round-specific buffers are indicated with an **ii** at the end of their name.
 - They must be unique as well; e.g., using `w_ii` and `w_stringent_ii` will lead to conflicts, since the string `w_` can match both buffers.
- Please note that after the name, you have to add ":" and then the position.

Examples

```
buffer: wash           general purpose buffer "wash"
buffer: w_r1           round specific buffer w_ for r1 (is defined as w_ii in the protocol sequence)
buffer: h_r1           round specific buffer h_ for r1 (is defined as h_ii in the protocol sequence)
buffer: w_r1           round specific buffer w_ for r2 (is defined as w_ii in the protocol sequence)
```

5.3.1.2 Positions

Positions are provided with a tuple with 3 elements: `[valve-id, plate-id, plate-pos]`

- **valve-id:** which port of the computer-controlled valve, e.g., with 8 entries.
 - 0: no valve used (because no valve in the fluidics system)

- >0: port entry number
- **plate-id:** several plates could be put on the robot
 - 0: no plate -> position as to be specified with XYZ coordinates (see below)
 - 1: plate 1 -> position must be specified with the well number (A1, ...)
- **plate-pos:**
 - For absolute positions you must specify the position relative to 0 position when homing the robot. To go to position (X=135mm, Y=36mm, Z=-39mm), you must specify `X135_Y36_Z-39`. Important are the underscores, and the minus (-) for the Z coordinate since the robot will move down.
 - For the well position, you can use A1, A2, ... The program calculated the absolute position based on the [well plate specification](#) that you provided.

Note: For buffers on the syringe stand, `plate-id` and `plate-pos` must be set to null.

Example

We defined two buffers, the general buffer `wash_valve4`, which can be found on valve 4, and the buffer `w_r1`, which will be used in an iterative run, which is on the first 96-well plate, on valve 6 in well A1:

```
buffers:
  wash_valve4: [4,null,null]
  w_r1: [6,1,A1]
```

5.3.2 valve_out

This is an optional field to specify outlet valves. We use these valves to direct the flow to different samples, e.g., different channels on an Ibidi multi-channel slide. The provided list contains the position IDs of each valve. In the example below, an outlet valve with 3 positions (5, 6, 7) is used.

```
valve_out:
  positions: [5,6,7]
```

5.3.3 sequence

Here, the sequence of steps to be executed is specified. Each step starts with a dash, and the steps are executed in the order listed from top to bottom. The following steps are supported.

Command	Action	Example
buffer	Select the specified buffer. Buffer names are listed with their position in the dedicated section "buffer" explained below. Buffer names containing 'ii' are buffers that are hybridization round specific and can be selected (more below).	- <code>buffer: wash_valve4</code>
pump	Activate the pump for the indicated duration in seconds.	- <code>pump: 180</code>
pump_valve_out	Activate the pump for the indicated duration for each of the specified outlet valves. Requires the definition of <code>valve_out</code> (see above). Number of parameters of durations must match the number of specified valve positions.	- <code>pump_valve_out: [180,30,30]</code>

pause	Take a break for the specified duration in seconds.	- <code>pause: 1200</code>
round	Specify conditional steps that are performed only for the indicated identifiers for a round (e.g. to perform a DAPI stain). Note that command has an additional indent. Multiple rounds can be defined and must be listed separated by a “,” and nothing else.	- - <code>round: r1,r4</code> - <code>buffer: dapi_ii</code>
zero_plate	Moves plate to position 0. This can be useful if during an experiment a plate should be changed (can be combined with <code>wait</code> to stop the system)	- <code>zero_plate:</code>
wait	Waits for the user to press ENTER. Can be used if some changes must be done to the system.	- <code>wait:</code>
image	Binary value (0 or 1) to indicate if an acquisition should be launched. This is usually interesting for conditional rounds (see <code>round</code> above) when now imaging should be performed.	- <code>image: 1</code>

Example 1: select the buffer `wash` and then activate the pump for 90s, you can write:

```
sequence:
- buffer: wash
- pump: 180
```

Example 2: The system has three outlet valves. The following command will select the first valve and activate the pump for 180s, then select the second and third valves and activate the pump for 30s each. The longer duration for the first valve allows the entire system to fill, while the subsequent durations are shorter because the buffer only fills the lines from the outlet valve to the sample support.

```
sequence:
- pump_valve_out: [180,30,30]
```

5.3.3.1 Conditional steps

You can define conditional steps that will be executed only for a specific hybridization run. For example, you want to include a DAPI wash for the first round. For this, you must use an indented sequence as shown below, where the first action is “round” followed by the identifier of the round, where these steps are to be performed. Please also note how the dashes are used. You can use all actions detailed above, including round-specific buffers, which will then only be used for these conditional runs.

In the **example** below, an additional buffer (`dapi_ii`) is used for rounds `r1` and `r4`.

```
- - round: r1,r4
- buffer: dapi_ii
- pump: 180
- pause: 180
```

5.3.4 well_plate

Here, the specifics of the used well plate are specified. This usually must be done once for a given configuration.

Command	Action	Default
top_right	Position of upper right well (center)	x: 63 y: 99
bottom_left	Position of bottom left well (center)	x: 0 y: 0
columns	Number of columns	8
rows	Number of rows	12
well_spacing	Distance between well	9
z_base	How much robot will go down in z [mm]	-37

Information will be used to automatically calculate the positions of each well (this can also include a tilt, i.e., a plate that is not aligned with the X and Y axes of the robot). The assumed orientation of the plate is indicated in the figure below. This means

- **Columns** are letters (A-G for a 96-well plate)
- **Rows** are numbered (1-12 for a 96-well plate)

5.4 Flow sensor

As an optional step, flow rates can be measured and compared to the expected flow when the pump is active. By defining tolerance limits, the fluidics system can be automatically stopped when the measured flow is outside of this tolerance.

5.4.1 Sensirion SLF3x Flow Sensor

We use a flow sensor from Sensirion (SO-SLF3S-0600F-EVAL-KIT). The evaluation kit connects it directly to a USB port. Rather than reading the flow rates directly into Python, we use the provided Viewer software available on the Sensirion website. This software allows you to log the flow rates into a CSV file. In autoFISH, we read this csv file and extract the expected volume for the specified pump duration.

In the system config file, you then must specify the location of this log file. Also, before activating the pump, make sure to record the flow in the file. The image below shows how to start the viewer software and start logging to a file (in this example, the flow sensor is on COM10):

1. Start software "USB RS485 Sensor Viewer"

2. In interface, select (order is important!):
 - a. COM Hardware: **RS485/USB Sensor Cable**
 - b. Sensor Product: **Liquid Flow Sensor (SF06 Chip)**
 - c. COM port: **COM10**

3. In new interface, start logging by
 - a. Measurement control
 - i. Sampling interval: **50ms**
 - ii. To start measurement, press button **Run**
 - b. Data logging
 - i. Select file: **C:\Temp\DataLog.csv** (default)
 - ii. To start logging, press button **Start logging**

6 Adding new components

The Python code is modular and allows adding new components.

6.1 Fluidics system

Communication with the fluidic system is handled by `automator.py`. Here, the class `Robot` controls the fluidics system, e.g., performing a sequence of buffer exchange steps.

Then each component is specified with its own class.

- `flowsensor`
- `plateController`
- `pumpController`
- `valveController`

Each base class defines the **required methods** that must be available. Each new component is then implemented as a new class derived from this class, e.g., for the Longer peristaltic pump, we created the class `LongerBT100` derived from the `pumpController` class.

Once a new class is implemented, the corresponding function `assign_XYZ` in the `Robot` class must be amended to include the new component, where `XYZ` is either `sensor`, `valve`, `pump`, or `plate`. Here, depending on the name used for this class in the `system_config` file, the object's initialization is defined.

For example,

- The Longer pump is specified in the system config file as type `LONGER BT100`.
- In the `assign_pump` class, the initiation of the pump object is performed with the `LongerBT100` class when the type corresponds to `LONGER BT100`.

6.2 Microscope communication

We implemented the class `Microscope` that has one required method `acquire_image`. Different classes can be derived from this class to initiate communication with the microscope. For instance, `pycroManager` to interact with Micromanager, or `TTL_sync` to initiate synchronization via a TTL pulse.

If new classes are implemented, they also must be considered in the GUI to be available in the pull-down menu (function `autofish_gui.py`).

7 Appendix

7.1 System configuration: system_config.json

In this JSON file, the communication protocol with the different hardware components is specified. Currently, four different components are permitted; for each one, a parent Python class is defined in autofish, specifying the minimal requirements for required methods. Then, a child class can be defined for a specific hardware platform.

- `pump`: defines a class for a pump. It must support at least these methods:
 - `start`: start the pump.
 - `stop`: stop the pump.
- `valve_in`: computer-controlled valve. Used to selected buffer (input valve)
- `valve_out`: computer-controlled valve. Used to select different outputs (output valve)
- `plate`: plate robot permitting access to many buffers, either in 96-well plates or in larger reservoirs.
- `flow_sensor`: sensor to measure flow rates.

The only required field is `'type'`, which identifies the exact component connected. All other fields are component-specific. For instance, for components connected via the serial port, information about the COM port and serial port protocol (baud rate) is provided.

Below, the configuration file for our fluidics system is shown:

```
{
  "pump": {
    "test_command": "1#\r",
    "response": "REGLO DIGITAL",
    "type": "REGLO DIGITAL",
    "baudrate": 9600,
    "COM": "COM10",
    "Revolution": "CCW",
    "Flowrate": 0.5
  },
  "valve_in": {
    "test_command": "/1h30001R\r",
    "response": "/0",
    "type": "HAMILTON MVP",
    "baudrate": 9600,
    "COM": "COM11"
  },
  "plate": {
    "type": "Robot GRBL",
    "wake_up": "\r\n\r\n",
    "test_command": "$I\n",
    "response": "VER:",
    "baudrate": 115200,
    "COM": "COM8",
    "feed": 115200,
  },
  "flow_sensor": {
    "type": "Sensirion CSV",
    "log_file": "C:\\Temp\\DataLog.csv",
    "kernel_size": 20,
    "flow_min": 20
  }
}
```

```
}  
}
```

7.2 Serial port communication

- <https://pythonhosted.org/pyserial/>
- <https://github.com/pyserial/pyserial>
- <https://www.com-port-monitoring.com/> (be careful to download the free version)

8 References

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9 Version history

Version	Date	Modified by	Changes
v1a	31.10.2024	Mueller F	Initial version for autoFISH bioarXiv.
v2	1.3.2025	Mueller F	Resubmission of autoFISH paper. Improved for clarity.
V3	1.3.2026	Mueller F	Diverse reformatting.